

Researcher mobility, co-authorship and individual research agendas

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This study investigates whether researchers whose published research record is more thematically broad —covering more, and more semantically distant, topics— are also characterized by specific patterns in their mobility between research organizations and countries and their co-authorship patterns. We study a large sample of productive authors in STEM fields who have been active in Germany. Our results show that specific types of international mobility go together with slightly elevated epistemic breadth. But scientists with larger co-author networks have relatively greater epistemic breadth. Finally, some disciplines, such as geosciences and astronomy, are comprised of researchers with low average epistemic breadth, while others, primarily computer science subfields, have many high-epistemic breadth researchers.

1. Introduction

One of the epistemic dimensions along which individual scientists differ is the structure of their research agenda in terms of the number and coherence of topics they work on. This dimension spans the poles from strict specialization on a single topic, which is investigated in ever greater depth, to, on the other end, the pursuit of a wide range of topics of quite different content (high heterogeneity or diversification). We refer to this concept as *epistemic breadth*, as the research portfolio of scientists may extend over a narrower or broader ‘area’ of the total knowledge space.

Earlier research has revealed a wide range of influences on researchers’ epistemic choices and research agendas, such as idiosyncratic individual personality (Bateman & Hess, 2015) and interest in subject matter (Garvey & Tomita, 1972), intermediate-level factors such as sectoral labor market fluctuations (Borjas & Doran, 2015), competitive pressure (Hagstrom, 1974), science political interventions (Gläser & Laudel, 2015), national career systems (Laudel, 2017), and more mundane local contingencies such as group leaders’ decisions (Garvey & Tomita, 1972; Hackett, 2005; Kaltenbrunner, 2018) or administrative appointments (Gerashchenko, 2024).

In the literature, the nature of the relationship between changing one’s research topics, or ‘cognitive mobility’, and physical mobility, moving between organizations and countries, has not received a lot of attention. Are these two phenomena independent, loosely, or closely related, perhaps mutually reinforcing each other? In this article, we explore in which ways epistemic breadth is related to physical mobility. Changing one’s location might be linked with an interest for broadening one’s thematic portfolio. Recent research has shown that researchers are increasingly

maintaining several topics throughout their career either simultaneously or subsequently (Gläser & Laudel, 2015; Horlings & Gurney, 2013).

Or is it rather co-authorship that stimulates and conditions researchers' exploration of new intellectual territory (Dubois, Rochet, & Schlenker, 2014; Leahey & Reikowsky, 2008; Pierce, 1999)? Here we study relations between a newly developed bibliometric measure of epistemic breadth and these factors of the scientific environment of researchers – institutional career stations (indicated by changes in affiliation and country) and co-authorship patterns.

In addition, it is not well understood how patterns of epistemic breadth differ between scientific disciplines, as most studies are restricted to a single discipline. Therefore, a further question we will address is that of disciplinary differences: Do scientific disciplines differ in the typical epistemic breadth? Epistemic conditions for changing or widening ones thematic portfolio are different among the disciplines. While in some fields, topical changes are expected, other fields encourage specialization or stabilization of research methods and objects (Laudel & Bielick, 2018).

2. Data and methods

2.1 Sample description

We investigate the statistical associations of scientists' epistemic breadth with other individual-level characteristics for a sample of particular interest for our research project, using the bibliometric database Scopus as the source of our data. Our sample is restricted to researchers who have published at least once with a German affiliation. We tallied publications of types article and review in the sciences, excluding the social sciences and humanities by not counting publications classified as Scopus All Science Journal Classification codes beginning with 12, 14, 20, and 33. This is because their research, to a large extent not written in English and often published in books, is not well covered in Scopus. We then retained those scientists (Scopus author IDs) with at least ten publications in order to obtain sufficiently statistically reliable individual-level scores. Thus, our author set does not include researchers never affiliated officially with a German address, early career researchers, most social scientists and humanities scholars, and those who have published few publications.

2.2 Affiliation data

Scopus Affiliation IDs were used to calculate authors' numbers of different institutional affiliations. We do not count it as a new institution if a researcher returns to an institution which they have previously been working for. The Scopus affiliation disambiguation algorithm does not always completely group different variants of affiliation strings under one organization ID (cf. Donner, Rimmert, & van Eck (2020)). We have therefore statistically corrected affiliation ID counts according to a manual sample analysis, not reported here due to space constraints.

2.3 Co-authorship data

We also use an indicator for the co-authorship propensity of a researchers. This is based on the number of different authors with whom a researcher has published. There are vast differences in co-authorship practices between disciplines, from a prevalence of solo authorship to hyper-authorship with thousands of co-authors on some papers. For papers with many authors, it can be

assumed that any author has closely collaborated only with a quite limited subset of all listed authors, simply due to constraints of time and effort, with a lot of coordination and integration handled by supervising researchers. We also know that all but a few of the most involved co-authors on many-authored papers have contributed relatively little. We are primarily interested in non-trivial co-authors, those whose collaboration was more than incidental. There are now validated statistical models which capture the generally prevailing distribution of contributions to co-authored publications reasonably well (Donner, 2020; Hagen, 2008). Based on the harmonic co-author credit model, which assigns a fraction of credit to authors based on their position in the author list and the number of co-authors, we calculated for all co-authors of a given author the sum of harmonic co-author credits from their co-published papers. We then calculated the number of co-authors whose sum exceeds 0.25, i.e. a quarter of a solo-authored publication. We call this indicator the filtered co-author count.

2.4 Normalized epistemic breadth

Our measure for the epistemic breadth of the published research of a scientist is built using semantic embeddings of papers’ titles and abstracts for which we use the SPECTER model (Cohan, Feldman, Beltagy, Downey, & Weld, 2020). Calculating the cosine similarity between embedding vectors of two papers results in a value that represents the semantic content similarity of these publications. The raw breadth score is calculated by finding, for each paper of a researcher, the semantically most distant other paper in their oeuvre and averaging all the furthest-neighbor semantic similarity scores. Validation results for this measure cannot be reported here due to space constraints.

The correlation between raw score epistemic breadth and the number of years actively publishing is -0.33. This is theoretically expected as researchers with longer careers have had more time and opportunity to enlarge their knowledge portfolio and publish on different topics. In order to make comparisons between

Table 1: Average normalized epistemic breadth of researchers grouped by international mobility

mobility group	avg. NEB	Q1	Q3	N	avg. years active
domestic	-0.089	-0.771	0.532	58028	12.285
inward remaining	-0.049	-0.720	0.541	20230	13.108
inward transitory	0.082	-0.634	0.695	52542	15.367
outward remaining	0.007	-0.694	0.605	22850	14.260
outward returnee	0.072	-0.598	0.673	23164	14.683

individuals of different publishing career lengths more easy and valid, it is convenient to create a new variable for epistemic breadth which is a deviation score from the expected value, namely the average raw score of researchers active for the same length of time, and to inverse the raw scores

such that higher values indicate higher epistemic breadth. We will refer to this as normalized epistemic breadth (NEB). It is important to note that this is not a population standardized score as we have selected a very specific subgroup of researchers.

3 Results

3.1 Statistical summary

The sample contains data on 176814 researchers. They have been active for an average of 14 years and contributed to 44 publications on average (median: 26). Taking into account their period of activity, this is an average of 3.2 publications per year. Most researchers were active in one (33 %) or two (36 %) countries, 19 % were active in three countries. Less than 13 % were affiliated with more than three countries. The sampled researchers were on average affiliated with 3.8 organizations (corrected estimates; median: 3). 59 % had their first affiliation in Germany. Adjusted for activity period, this is 0.3 different affiliations per year on average. According to the filtered co-author count, the researchers collaborated with an average number of 32 researchers (median: 20) to a non-trivial extent by our convention. This is 2.3 non-trivial co-authors per year active.

3.2 Bivariate relationships

3.2.1 Epistemic breadth of international mobility groups

We categorized researchers with respect to their mobility relative to Germany into five distinct categories. Those who only ever published with an affiliation in Germany, the largest group, are referred to as ‘domestic’. Those who first published abroad, then had an affiliation in Germany, and later moved on abroad, are referred to as ‘inward transitory’. They are the second largest group. Those who first published abroad, came to Germany and remained there at the final point of data collection, are referred to as ‘inward remaining’. They may or may not have repeatedly left and returned to Germany in the meantime. Those who first were affiliated with an institution in Germany, then moved abroad and were abroad at the time of data collection, we call ‘outward remaining’. Finally, the fifth group are those whose first affiliation was a German one, moved abroad but had returned to Germany. They are called ‘outward returnees’. These latter three groups are about the same size. We have calculated average NEB and years active for the five international mobility categories in table 1.

The table shows that the epistemic breadth of ‘domestic’ researchers is lowest, about 0.1 sd below expectation for their activity period. They are also the group with the shortest activity period. The group of ‘inward remaining’ researchers have a average NEB 0.04 sd below their expectation while having the longest average activity periods. The group ‘outward remaining’ have about typical epistemic breadth. The two groups which might be considered most internationally mobile, ‘inward transitory’ and ‘outward returnee’, have

Table 2: Average number of affiliations by NEB quartile

NEB quartile	N	avg. affiliations	avg. countries
Q1	44204	3.225	2.063
Q2	44203	3.622	2.157
Q3	44204	3.996	2.250
Q4	44203	4.350	2.357

elevated average NEB values of about 0.09 and 0.07 sd, respectively. Recall that researchers of these groups have made at least two international affiliation changes in their careers. These data indicate that it is not so much the experience of any international mobility as such that is associated with higher epistemic breadth but specific patterns. The groups of ‘outward remaining’ and ‘inward remaining’ researchers have also been internationally mobile yet their average NEB scores are around zero and below zero, respectively. Restricting the analysis to researchers active for about the same duration does not qualitatively alter the findings.

Columns Q1 and Q3 show the values of first and third quartile of the NEB distribution for the groups. The central 50% of values fall between these two limits. This provides some important context for the results reported above. While the distributions are shifted up or down depending on the averages, still there is broad overlap. That is to say, in each mobility group there are plenty of researchers with low, intermediate, and high epistemic breadth. In summary, while we do find evidence for differences in typical epistemic breadth between international mobility groups, the size of these differences is small compared to the variability within groups.

3.2.2 Epistemic breadth and organizational and international mobility

We find a moderate statistical association between the normalized epistemic breadth score of researchers and the estimated corrected number of different organizational affiliations they have reported (Pearson correlation coefficient of $r=0.174$), such that researchers with broader knowledge profiles have worked at more organizations. Table 2 shows the size of the effect of this relationship. The sample has been split into four equal-sized quartiles according to the value of the NEB scores and the average number of estimated affiliations have been calculated for the four groups. It can be seen that there is a clear monotonous increase in affiliations as the level of epistemic breadth of researchers goes up, to the extent of one affiliation more for the highest as compared to the lowest quartile group. This is quite a large difference considering the range of the group averages. Further, the average number of different countries from which the researchers have published have been calculated for the same four quartile groups (also in table 2). The results mirror those for affiliations, but the group differences are not as notable. Low-NEB researchers have worked in 2.0 countries on average, high-NEB researchers in 2.3 countries.

3.3 Epistemic breadth across disciplines

We have assigned each of the nearly 177,000 productive researchers affiliated with Germany to their most common discipline category according to the Scopus ASJC, a journal-level classification for publications. We interpret such a main category as a somewhat crude

approximation of their main field of research activity, yet sufficient for the purpose of revealing larger-scale differences in epistemic breadth on the level of disciplines. 175 of these categories have more than 100 researchers in the sample and it is these we analyze further. Table 3 summarizes the ASJC classes with the lowest average researcher NEB. The disciplines with low epistemic breadth researchers are geosciences, astronomy, non-human biological, and agricultural science subfields. The disciplines with high epistemic breadth are displayed in table 4. These are primarily subfields of computer science and also include statistics and general psychology. These disciplinary tendencies are quite strong, with discipline averages of epistemic breadth deviating up to 1 sd from the grand mean in either direction while showing comparable variabilities within disciplines. These disciplinary and subfield differences in epistemic breadth are far greater than those reported above for international mobility groups, suggesting a major role for knowledge factors or possibly socio-traditional disciplinary differences in influencing epistemic breadth

Table 3: Lowest average NEB Scopus ASJC disciplines

Scopus ASJC category	avg. NEB	sd NEB	N
Paleontology	-1.073	0.846	286
Geology	-0.955	0.997	566
Oceanography	-0.711	1.014	413
Earth-Surface Processes	-0.702	0.901	423
Astronomy and Astrophysics	-0.677	0.922	4183
Parasitology	-0.657	1.023	112
Horticulture	-0.636	0.984	119
Insect Science	-0.614	0.971	169
Geophysics	-0.598	0.952	912
Plant Science	-0.596	0.916	2145

Table 4: Highest average NEB Scopus ASJC disciplines

Scopus ASJC category	avg. NEB	sd NEB	N
Human-Computer Interaction	1.409	1.002	140
Artificial Intelligence	1.300	1.022	385
Computer Networks and Communications	1.260	1.180	659
Software	1.260	1.169	525
Information Systems	1.207	0.984	296
Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition	1.201	1.045	179
Computer Science (all)	1.157	1.139	864
Health Informatics	1.134	0.991	142
Statistics and Probability	1.100	1.168	508
Control and Systems Engineering	1.085	1.142	503

of researchers. However, at this stage of our research we cannot confidently exclude the possibility that our breadth measure may not be invariant across disciplines, for example because of imbalances in training data across disciplines in the embeddings model.¹ Therefore, we caution against interpreting these results as definitive.

3.4 Epistemic mobility and co-authorship

There is a strong association between the filtered co-author count and epistemic breadth. Table 5 reports the average co-author counts for the quartiles of researchers as grouped by NEB. High-NEB researchers (Q4) have on average twice as many co-authors as the low epistemic breadth group (Q1).

3.5 Multiple regression analysis of researchers' epistemic mobility

All of the investigated variables are in some way statistically associated with epistemic mobility. To test which ones are still associated with NEB in an analysis controlling for confounding, we estimate an ordinary least squares regression model with NEB as the dependent variable and the other variables discussed above as independent variables. The country count, organization count, and years active variables were standardized,

Table 5: Average number of filtered co-authors by NEB quartile

NEB quartile	N	avg. co-authors
Q1	44204	21.410
Q2	44203	28.401
Q3	44204	35.616
Q4	44203	42.871

so the magnitude of their coefficients can be compared. The publication count variable was logarithmized and standardized. The results are shown in table 6, except for the numerous coefficients for the ASJC codes for researchers' main discipline, which are omitted. Only a moderate proportion of the variance, about 20 % can be explained by the model predictors in the full model, Model 1. All included variables are found to be statistically significant. The sizes of the estimated coefficients for the number different countries and adjusted co-author count are small in this model in which the other variables are controlled for. In fact, the sign of the coefficient for

¹ Disciplinary differences in average epistemic breadth are challenging to analyze because a fundamental precondition is that the measurement instrument has to be invariant across scientific disciplines. A semantic distance of 0.1 units between to publications in philosophy should mean the same degree of difference in content as 0.1 units distance in chemistry. It is hard to establish measurement invariance for our operationalization based on semantic distances between publications as there is no external empirical yardstick that could be used to test whether the measured semantic distances in an embeddings model are equally reliable and comparable throughout the entire knowledge space of the model.

number of countries is negative, unlike in the bivariate analysis. The effect of the number of publications is large and positive. Conversely, that of the length of active publishing career is large and negative. Recall that the dependent variable, NEB, is standardized by years of publication activity. The effects of international mobility group confirm the prior bivariate analysis in that the other groups have higher NEB than the reference category, domestic researchers, after controlling for other factors. The association of NEB and the number of different organizations remains significant in the multiple regression analysis but the effect size is minor. Model 2 is a reduced model in which the discipline variable dummies, the researchers' main ASJC codes, have been removed. In contrast to Model 1's 20 % explained variance, this model only achieves 9 % explained variance, confirming that it is the disciplinary-specific factors captured by this variable which have the strongest associations with epistemic breadth independently of other variables.

4 Discussion

We have studied the relations of several individual-level factors and broader epistemic variables with our measure of researchers' epistemic breadth. We find that researchers who move more between organizations and countries also have higher epistemic breadth index values, that is, they work on more diverse topics than their more 'stationary' colleagues. Authors who work with more co-authors are show elevated epistemic breadth. Finally, we reported notable difference across scientific disciplines. A combined analysis of these relations in a multiple regression with NEB as the dependent variable revealed some further insights. For instance, the number of different countries is no longer positively correlated with epistemic breadth after partialling out the effects of other factors such as main discipline. Another observation from the regression analysis is that even though we found major disciplinary differences, controlling for this variable did not render the effects of other variables insignificant.

The major limitation of our study is that we were only able to study a few bibliometric factors for their influence on epistemic breadth, not personal/demographic or broader societal factors. Further, our design permits no statements as to causality. In fact this would be difficult with bibliometric data. Consider that we would like to know if changing jobs and affiliation causes a change of research topic or if a decision to explore a new research topic triggered a search for a new position elsewhere. Whatever the direction may be, it seems probable that in bibliometric data we could only observe both a topic change and an affiliation change at the same time, namely in the first publication on the new topic published from the new affiliation. The same logic holds for the expansion of the co-authorship network. Further informed qualitative field research of selected individuals from different mobility groups would allow gaining more information on the contextual factors that shape epistemic breadth and further deepen the understanding of the interaction of physical mobility and epistemic breadth.

Table 6. Regression models

	Model 1	Model 2
Intercept	1.429 (0.892)	-0.031 (0.005)***
publications	0.316 (0.004)***	0.349 (0.004)***
different countries	-0.020 (0.004)***	-0.061 (0.004)***
different organizations	0.057 (0.003)***	0.103 (0.003)***
adjusted co-author count	0.013 (0.004)***	-0.041 (0.004)***
years active	-0.208 (0.003)***	-0.192 (0.003)***
international mobility groups, ref.: domestic		
inward remaining	0.067 (0.008)***	0.013 (0.009)
inward transitory	0.106 (0.007)***	0.054 (0.008)***
outward remaining	0.112 (0.008)***	0.082 (0.009)***
outward returnee	0.040 (0.008)***	0.022 (0.008)**
R ²	0.206	0.094
Adj. R ²	0.205	0.094
Num. obs.	176814	176814

coefficients for ASJC disciplines codes omitted

Open science practices

This paper uses proprietary licenced bibliometric data which cannot be made available under the licencing terms.

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Author contributions

PD: Conceptualization, Software, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing—original draft

CB: Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing—review & editing, Project administration

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

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